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Modelling the enslaved as historical persons

Extending the Persons in Context (PiCo) model to fit enslaved individuals

Multiple parties in the Netherlands publish open data on persons who lived in the former Dutch colonies in the Caribbean, Asia, and Africa in collaboration with knowledge and heritage partners and citizen scientists throughout these regions and the Netherlands (see e.g. Konings et al., 2023; Petram & Van Rossum, 2022; Van Galen et al., 2023; [HDSC Dataverse](#); [Globalise Dataverse](#)). As a result of these collaborations, historical person observations have been collected that can be used to reconstruct enslaved individuals as historical persons. To make these person observations and reconstructions interoperable and accessible to the general and scholarly public, the use of a clear and systematic data model is required.

Exchange of large volumes of data between different parties puts specific requirements on the data. For example, data needs to be shared and curated on a large scale. To accommodate this, the Dutch Digital Heritage Network (NDE) and Ministry of Education, Culture, and Science (2021; 2024) have appointed the Semantic Web as the standard for digital heritage data. The advantage of the Semantic Web, also known as the Resource Description Framework (RDF) or Linked Data, is that each bit of information in a dataset is described with a unique URI, which can be represented as Uniform Resource Locators (URLs) to retrieve and describe entities or properties. As a result, the Semantic Web makes it possible to effectively exchange data and write software, as long as multiple parties use the same URIs.

In order to effectively communicate (historical) person data, the Dutch Center for Family History (CBG) has developed the [Persons in Context](#) (PiCo) model (Woltjer et al., 2024), on the basis of the ROAR model developed by Menno den Engelse and Leon van Wissen (2021). The PiCo model states how information on common factors in historical person observations, such as age, dates of birth, marriage, and death, occupations, relations between family members, roles in source documents, etc. should be described. We chose to implement this model for our own databases with historical person data on enslaved people, as the PiCo model for the integration of all historical person observations and provides flexibility and guidelines for extending the model according to the requirements of specific historical data sets. The PiCo model is sustained by a PiCo maintenance group, consisting of the Center for Family History and multiple archival as well as research institutions.

The PiCo model reuses as many existing URIs as possible to describe historical person data. Allowing communities to give the same name to the same entity prevents discussions on naming and describing resources that have already been authoritatively defined, such as birth dates or names. It also makes data more findable as people can search on one common term rather than having to waste time on resolving a potentially endless list of variations in modelling the same concept. But, perhaps even more importantly, it enforces stringent definitions of properties and resources that can be used for efficient knowledge interfering.

Implementing the Persons in Context model

Reuse of data is easiest when data is described concentrically, which involves reusing general, domain-specific, and specialised schemas for resources that are commonly known in the world, domain, or field in question (Meroño-Peñuela et al., 2020; Mourits et al., 2024). Since most resources have already been described within the PiCo model and specialized concepts can be adopted from the history of slavery domain, it becomes relatively easy to model data describing historical persons living in conditions of slavery.

For global concepts, [Schema.org](https://schema.org) and [Wikidata.org](https://wikidata.org) are logical options (Woltjer et al., 2024; Min OCW & NDE, 2024). Within the history of slavery, [Enslaved.org](https://enslaved.org) has used the Semantic Web technology to describe enslaved people (Hawthorne et al. 2023; Shimizu et al., 2023). In their approach, they described all concepts encountered in historical databases on enslavement in their own data model. Sadly, the Enslaved.org model is not reusable for our data in its entirety, because their event-based model is not compatible with the concentric description used in the PiCo-model. Nevertheless, we are very enthusiastic about the Enslaved project's efforts to provide domain-specific terms that can enhance the interoperability of data sets relating to slavery.

By incorporating selected elements of the Semantic Web vocabularies of the [Schema.org](https://schema.org), [Wikidata.org](https://wikidata.org), and [Enslaved.org](https://enslaved.org) in the design of the Persons in Context model, we were able to convert the 1828-1847 Paramaribo Ward Registers (Sang-Ajang et al., 2024) and the 1830-1863 Surinam Slave Registers (Rosenbaum-Feldbrügge et al., 2023) into ttl format¹. On a few occasions, we were forced to create new properties required to accurately model the data. Rather than introducing new properties ourselves, we would prefer to refer to [Enslaved.org](https://enslaved.org) properties in these cases. However, we were unable to reach a consensus with [Enslaved.org](https://enslaved.org) on how to model these properties.

Presenting a use case: re-linking identities of urban enslaved persons

To show the practical advantage of working with the extended data model, we wish to demonstrate at the DH BeNeLux 2025:

- a) The problems in modeling historical person data slave societies. There are incongruencies between the Enslaved.org ontology/thesaurus and the inherent logic behind the PiCo model which need adaptation. Moreover, there are elements which both PiCo and Enslaved.org address inadequately, including toponymic associations in names, social categories, organizational slaveholders, freedom status, and

¹ see also: <https://github.com/HDSC-Nijmegen/Slavenregisters/tree/main/ttl%20conversion> and <https://github.com/HDSC-Nijmegen/Ward-registers>

specialized enslavement relationships. These concepts are either not modelled or too context-specific to be reused flexibly.

- b) What the added value of the Semantic Web is by linking, and thereby enriching, information about enslaved individuals and their enslavers across various sources available as structured data, such as the Suriname Slave Registers, the Paramaribo Ward Registers, and several plantation datasets. We should be able to match graphs with standardised protocols, as all entities and properties in the graph are already standardised and should require little to no data transformation. Added advantage is that we actually test the extended data model in practice, which will no doubt highlight additional issues;
- c) How the results can be shared in a data story and other online formats.

Lessons learned and way forward

Using the Enslaved.org vocabularies we extended the Persons in Context model, so that it can also be used to describe the lives of enslaved persons. Following the methodology of concentric description, we reused existing terminology on the Semantic Web to describe our data. Our goal is to make the extended model also suitable for different historical periods, such as the 17th, 18th, and 19th centuries, and regions, such as Asia and the Caribbean. However, before doing so, we first needed to implement a workflow that dealt with finding concepts not readily available in the original PiCo model.

We reached out to the PiCo maintenance group to ask for feedback on how best to proceed. We explained how we extended the PiCo model by reusing Enslaved.org URIs to describe our data, and enquired whether PiCo could implement a few proposed properties which were not provided by [Enslaved.org](https://enslaved.org)—at least not in the way we wanted. The feedback from the PiCo maintenance group was that extensions to the PiCo model should come from authoritative concepts in specialised fields.² They further stated that:

- The extension of the PiCo model is a best practice because it is reusing a specialized vocabulary.
- PiCo also wants to recommend such extensions in the long run if they are used more widely in a field.
- PiCo itself will not introduce new terminology if a specialized field does not provide it.

In other words, PiCo will not come up with property until there is consensus within the history of slavery domain. In order to approach consensus on modeling historical person data in the context of slavery, our first step was to set up a collaboration between the Historical Database of Suriname and the Caribbean (HDSC), GLOBALISE and Exploring Slave Trade in Asia (ESTA) projects.³ These three projects revolve around data on enslaved individuals in contexts of slavery in the Atlantic, as well as in the wider Indian Ocean world.

At the DH BeNeLux 2025 we hope to show the data model and discuss how it works in practice with a use case. Our goal here is fourfold. We want to show 1) the potential of the PiCo data model to reconstruct the lives of enslaved persons by combining multiple sources, 2) PiCo's current limits in modelling the lives of enslaved people, 3) how existing data

² see: <https://github.com/CBG-Centrum-voor-familiegeschiedenis/PiCo/issues/30>

³ for HDSC, see <https://hdsc.ning.com>; for GLOBALISE, see <https://globalise.huygens.knaw.nl>; for ESTA, see <https://esta.iisg.nl>.

models can be extended using community standards, and 4) a first glimpse of the reconstructed life course of the enslaved. This is only the beginning. We suspect that the wide range of colonial sources that PiCo aims to support will provide more insight into the lives of enslaved, which in turn will also raise new modelling issues.

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